

Spectrophotometric Determination of Rhenium with Rubeanic Acid

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Rubeanic acid produces a reddish-brown colouration with perrhenate in hydrochloric acid medium in presence of stannous chloride. The complex has no absorption maximum in the range 370-600 nm. Studies have been made at the wavelengths of 410, 420, 450 and 460 nm since the reagent has no absorption at and above 410 nm. Beer's law is obeyed from 1-70 ppm of rhenium at all these wavelengths. Composition of the complex as determined by Job and molar ratio methods is found to be 1 : 1 at all the wave-lengths studied. Stability constant was calculated by the methods of Harvey and Manning, Leden and Rossotti and Rossotti. A large number of ions do not interfere in the determination of rhenium.

A number of sulphur-bearing organic compounds^{1,2} have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. The present paper deals with the investigation of the reaction of rubeanic acid ($\text{NH}_2\text{CS}-\text{CSNH}_2$) with rhenium. It is seen that in most of the systems already studied, the Beer's law range is shorter than the one obtained with the present system. Some of the papers give molar absorptivity values without mentioning the Beer's law range. The molar absorptivity of the rhenium-rubeanic acid system can be compared satisfactorily with those of the other systems. The composition and stability constants of the complex in solution, found in the present case, have also been reported and these are conspicuous by their absence in many other cases. So far as the interferences are concerned, rubeanic acid complex has been observed to show great tolerance to common ions and tungsten(VI).

However, the complex of rhenium with rubeanic acid is not extractable in solvents like benzene, chloroform, amyl-acetate, iso-amyl alcohol, n-propyl alcohol, n-butyl alcohol and n-benzyl alcohol.

Experimental :

Apparatus and solutions :

A Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz transmission cells was used.

A standard rhenium (VII) solution was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity of potassium perrhenate (Johnson Matthey) in double-distilled water. The solution was standardised by internal electrolysis^{1,2}.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of rubeanic acid (G.R.E. Merck) was prepared in absolute ethanol.

1.7 M solution of stannous chloride (G.R.E. Merck) was prepared in 9 M hydrochloric acid.

Solutions of other ions were prepared from their chlorides, sulphates, or from their sodium, potassium or ammonium salts and were standardised according to the conventional methods. All other chemicals were of highest degree of purity.

Double-distilled water was used in all solution preparations.

Absorbance curve :

3 ml of the rubeanic acid (0.1% w/v) solution were added to a solution of perrhenate (120 μg of rhenium) in a 10 ml volumetric flask, followed by 1.5 ml of 1.7 M stannous chloride solution and hydrochloric acid to maintain the final normality between 1.5 and 2.1. This was diluted to 6 ml with the addition of a measured quantity of water. The mixture was then heated over a boiling water bath for 45 mins, cooled to room temperature and finally its volume was made upto 10 ml with dry ethanol. In the final solution the ratio of water to ethanol was maintained at 3:7. The final concentration of rhenium was 12 ppm. The absorbances of

Fig. 1 : Absorption spectra : 12 ppm of rhenium.

reddish-brown complex, thus formed, were measured at different wavelengths against a reagent blank similarly prepared. The colour did not show any maximum absorption in the range 370-600 nm (Fig. 1. a) Since the reagent has no absorption at and above 410 nm, subsequent measurements were done at the wavelengths of 410, 420, 450 and 460 nm ; these wavelengths were chosen arbitrarily.

Effect of heating, reagent, acidity, stannous chloride and time :

The full colour development of the complex was obtained after heating over a boiling water bath for a period of 40-50 mins.

Fig. 2 : Effect of variation of SnCl₂ concentration

- A Δ 410 nm
- B \bullet 420 nm
- C \circ 450 nm
- D \blacktriangle 460 nm

2.5 ml of the 0.1% ethanolic reagent solution were quite enough for the full colour development of 12 ppm of rhenium. Addition of more reagent (upto 5 ml) did not produce any adverse effect on

the colour system. For subsequent measurements (till 70 ppm of rhenium) about 3 ml of the reagent solution were found sufficient.

The optimum acid concentration required for maximum colour development was found to be between 1.5 and 2.1 N with respect to hydrochloric acid.

The colour intensity was found to increase with the increasing amount of stannous chloride (Fig.2). With the addition of more than 4 ml of 1.7 M SnCl₂ solution, the precipitate appeared and solution turned hazy. However, the intensity attained a constant value with 1.25 to 1.75 ml of 1.7 M SnCl₂ solution and no change in the nature of the absorption spectra was observed using further excess of SnCl₂. In all measurements, 1.5 ml of 1.7 M SnCl₂ solution in 9 M hydrochloric acid were used.

The colour intensity remained constant for 24 hours.

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error, sensitivity and molar absorptivity :

The colour system was found to obey Beer's law from 1-70 ppm of rhenium at all these wavelengths—410, 420, 450 and 460 nm. The absorbance could not be measured above 70 ppm of rhenium because of its high intensity.

The optimal concentration range was evaluated from the Ringbom curve¹⁴(Fig.3) and found as 10.0-50.0 ppm (410 nm), 10.0-50.0 ppm (420 nm), 17.4-50.0 ppm (450 nm) and 18.2-50.0 ppm (460 nm).

The % relative error per absolute photometric

Fig. 3 : Ringbom plots

- A Δ 410 nm
- B \bullet 420 nm
- C \circ 450 nm
- D \blacktriangle 460 nm

error was calculated according to the equation of Ayres¹⁵ and was found to be 2.72.

The Sandell sensitivities¹⁶ and molar absorptivities (calculated from Beer's law values) were $0.05186 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 3.6×10^3 at 410 nm, $0.05525 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 3.4×10^3 at 420 nm, $0.06476 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 2.9×10^3 at 450 nm and $0.07000 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 2.7×10^3 at 460 nm.

Composition of the complex :

The composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variation and by the molar ratio method. For Job's method, equimolar solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of rhenium and reagent were mixed in different proportions (12 ml of total mixture) in 25 ml volumetric flasks. It was followed by addition of 3.75 ml of 1.7 M stannous chloride solution and hydrochloric acid to maintain the final normality of the solution between 1.5 and 2.1. Measured quantity of water was added to make the volume of the aqueous portion 7.5 ml. The mixture was then heated over a boiling water bath for 45 mins, cooled to room temperature and finally its volume was made upto 25 ml with dry ethanol. In the final solution, the ratio of water to ethanol was maintained at 3 : 7. The absorbances of the solutions were measured at the wavelengths studied. Fig.4 indicates that in the solution rhenium and reagent are in the ratio of 1 : 1.

Fig. 4 : Curves by Job's method (equimolar) rhenium = reagent = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

- A Δ 410 nm
- B \bullet 420 nm
- C \circ 450 nm
- D \blacktriangle 460 nm
- E \ominus 585 nm

In molar ratio method, with the equimolar solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the rhenium and the

reagent, the concentration of rhenium was kept fixed and that of the reagent was varied. The break in the curve suggests the formation of the same 1 : 1 complex (Fig.5).

Fig. 5 : Molar ratio method rhenium = reagent = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, 6 ml of rhenium solution used.

- A Δ 410 nm
- B \bullet 420 nm
- C \circ 450 nm
- D \blacktriangle 460 nm
- E \ominus 585 nm

During the composition studies, it was observed that a green complex was formed only when a very little amount of the reagent solution (0.5 ml to 3.5 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) was added to a high excess of rhenium ($1117.5 \mu\text{g}$ of rhenium/25 ml) and the whole procedure for colour development was performed. The complex showed maximum absorption at 585 nm. But as this is very unstable its composition could not be determined. The decomposition of the green compound started during cooling slowly converting it to one of reddish-brown colour. This reddish-brown one is the same product, the results of the spectrophotometric and composition studies of which have been reported earlier in this paper and the identity of the two is discernable from their identical absorption spectra.

The formation of the green product does not affect the overall composition, as obtained by Job's and molar ratio methods at 410, 420, 450, 460 as also at 585 nm, where the same 1 : 1 complexes were obtained in all the cases (Figs. 4 and 5). This is because green product completely changed to reddish-brown one during measurements.

Degree of dissociation and stability constant :

The value of α , the degree of dissociation, was calculated from Harvey and Manning's equation¹⁷, and the instability constant K' was evaluated from the equation $K' = (m\alpha c)^m (n\alpha c)^n c(1-\alpha)$, [where $m=1$, $n=1$ in this case]. Then, the stability constant K was calculated as $1/K'$. The stability constant K was also evaluated by Leden's method¹⁸ (Fig. 6) and by the method of Rossotti and

Fig. 6 : Leden's method

Rossotti¹⁹(Fig.7). All the values were calculated at the wavelength of 450 nm and are given in Table 1.

Fig. 7 : Rossotti-Rossotti's method.

 TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF THE COMPLEX
 Havery and Manning

E_m	E_s	c	α	K	Leden's K	Rossotti & Rossotti K	Average K
0.670	0.346	0.24×10^{-5}	0.4835	9.2×10^8	14.6×10^8	7.6×10^8	10.5×10^8

The value of molar extinction co-efficient mentioned before, obtained from Beer's law, shows a close resemblance with the value ($\epsilon = 2.514 \times 10^3$) obtained from graphical evaluation¹⁹.

Effect of foreign ions :

It was observed that 20 ppm of rhenium tolerated the presence of the ions V^{5+} (50 ppm), Hg^{2+} (60 ppm), UO_2^{2+} (50 ppm), W^{6+} (20 ppm), Zr^{4+} (70 ppm) and large amounts of Al^{3+} , Be^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , TiO^{2+} , citrate, oxalate, EDTA (disodium salt) and tartrate. In presence of EDTA (disodium salt) the system tolerated the presence of Fe^{3+} (250 ppm), Ni^{2+} (230 ppm) and Zn^{2+} (180 ppm). However, interferences due to Pb^{2+} (125 ppm), UO_2^{2+} (200 ppm), W^{6+} (100 ppm) and Mn^{2+} (150 ppm) could be prevented by tartaric acid used as masking agent and that of Hg^{2+} (90 ppm) by oxalic acid. Os^{8+} , Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Mo^{6+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} and Cu^{2+} interfere. The oxidation states of the metal ions given above were the states before $SnCl_2$ treatment.

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